

Dual Acid-Tailored Ionic Covalent Organic Frameworks for High Temperature Proton Conduction Under Anhydrous Conditions and the Practical Opportunities

Vellaichamy Joseph[†], Keiichiro Maegawa[†], Mateusz Wlazło[‡], Marek J. Potrzebowski[⊥],
Krzysztof Łyczko[§], Atsushi Nagai^{*†}

[†] Next-Generation Energy Systems group, Centre of Excellence ENSEMBLE3 sp. z o.o.,
Wólczyńska 133, Warsaw 01-919, Poland.

[‡] Chemical and Biological Systems Simulation Lab, Centre of New Technologies, University of
Warsaw, Banacha 2c, Warsaw 02-097, Poland.

[⊥] Center of Molecular and Macromolecular Studies, Polish Academy of Sciences, Sienkiewicza 112,
Lodz 90-363, Poland.

[§] Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology, Dorodna 16, Warsaw 03-195, Poland.

E-mail: atsushi.nagai@ensemble3.eu

Abstract

An organic salt (DMAP/Pa-SO₃H) composed of 2,5-diaminobenzenesulfonic acid (Pa-SO₃H) and dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) was demonstrated as a linker to construct ionic covalent organic frameworks (iCOFs). The iCOF denoted as TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H was prepared by the condensation reaction of triformylphloroglucinol (Tp) building block and DMAP/Pa-SO₃H, and offers the potential to accommodate an external proton source (H₃PO₄; PA), enabling the immobilization of PA moieties within pore structure through strong ionic hydrogen bonding interaction evidenced by DFT calculations. Further, H₃PO₄-doped iCOF denoted as PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H proclaimed the advantage of engineering at the linker position which in turn promotes proton conductivity to $1.56 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ (increased 100-fold as related to PA@TpPa-SO₃H) at 140 °C under anhydrous conditions. Finally, we investigated the adaptability of a dual-acid system in sulfonated polyetheretherketone (SPEEK) membranes, a

common acid-modified polymeric material. PA doped DMAP modified SPEEK (PA@SPEEK/DMAP) evidenced a 100-fold appreciation of proton conductivity at 120 °C, as compared to bare SPEEK membranes under anhydrous conditions.

Introduction

Proton conduction is a unique process that is highly sought after in energy conversion and storage devices such as fuel cells, proton exchange membrane electrolyzers and redox flow batteries. In particular, proton-conducting materials employed in fuel cells are challenging to act as electrolytes for high temperature (>100 °C) polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells (HT-PEMFCs).^{1,2} The implementation of HT-PEMFCs is advantageous because it increases the reaction rate and reduces CO poisoning at the platinum electrode. It also eliminates the need for additional humidifiers, which greatly simplifies water management much easier.^{3,4} Currently, few materials offer the high proton conductivity and long durability required for commercial application, with the main exception being Nafion[®], a perfluorinated sulfonated polymer. However, the high cost, synthetic challenges and limited operating conditions hinder further applications.^{5,6} Further, it shows high performance mainly at low temperatures and high humidity, which is disadvantageous for operation under non-humidified conditions. Therefore, the development of alternative materials for the fabrication of proton-exchange membranes (PEMs) is of great importance and urgently needed. Generally, PEMs employ solid polymeric electrolytes that have high porosity, good structural robustness, the potential for easy membrane fabrication and the ability to transfer protons.⁷⁻¹⁰ These ionic polymer electrolytes include gel-like polymer structures that are highly swollen and carry fixed positive and negative charges. However, conventional organic polymers are amorphous which makes them difficult to control their precise structure and pore environment (i.e., pore size, shape, and exposed functional groups). Further, the relationship between structure and properties is not well understood.¹¹ Moreover, most of these polymers fail to have proton conducting properties in

dry conditions, but only in the moist state, and it is dependent on the amount of water (i.e. relative humidity) that makes them unfavorable for the HT-PEMFC applications.

Over the past 10 years, covalent organic frameworks (COFs) have emerged as a new class of crystalline porous organic polymer materials, showing great potential to overcome the limitations of conventional organic polymers due to their well-defined structure, high surface area, fine-tunable pore environment, and tailorable functionality.¹²⁻¹⁷ In 2016, the Banerjee group achieved proton conductivity ($\sim 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$) for phytic acid-loaded three component β -ketoenamine COF composed of sulfonic acid and pyridine linkers [denoted as phytic@TpPa-(SO₃H-Py)] under anhydrous condition (120 °C).¹⁸ The phytic acid-doped COFs with pyridine moieties showed the presence of the phytate anions regardless of their ionization degree, while phytic acid-loaded TpPa-SO₃H without pyridine moieties exhibited low proton conductivity. Therefore, we were inspired to design novel organic salt linker containing diaminobenzenesulfonic acid-modified dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) with two base moieties such as pyridine ring and dimethylamine group that could fix phosphoric acid (PA) inside the iCOF, counting on the improvement of both proton conductivity and thermal stability, and suppression of PA leakage.

Recently, we reported that the proton conductivity of ionic materials such as salts can be correlated using protonated interatomic distance (PAD) induced by the acid-base reaction between a strong electroreceptive acid and a strong donor base; accordingly, it was found that the shorter the PAD, the higher the proton conduction.¹⁹ For example, when the *para*-position of the pyridine ring is replaced by a strongly electron donating dimethylamine group, acid-base ionic compound exhibit a short PAD. Thus, it is speculated that dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) could be the most effective base motif for designing organic salt linkers and further to realize highly efficient proton-conducting COF materials.

Herein, we report the design and synthesis of a new phosphoric acid (PA)-loaded iCOF (PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H) containing β -ketoenamine backbone and organic salt linker, which enables a dramatic enhancement of proton conductivity under anhydrous conditions at 140 °C, and also higher conductivity at 80 °C under humidified conditions compared to those of PA-doped TpPa-SO₃H. In order to understand the interaction between salt moiety and PA, DFT calculation was performed for model salt compound ($\Delta pK_a = 7.1$) denoted as DMAP/bz-SO₃H, which is composed of benzenesulfonic acid (bz-SO₃H, $pK_a = -2.5$) and DMAP ($pK_a = 9.60$) (Scheme 1a). According to the pKa rule ($(\Delta pK_a > 2 \text{ or } 3 \text{ is salt})$),²⁰⁻²³ DMAP/bz-SO₃H is a salt moiety, and PA is placed near it (Scheme 1a). The calculated total binding energy ($E_{\text{PA}@\text{DMAP/bz-SO}_3\text{H}} - E_{\text{DMAP/bz-SO}_3\text{H}} - E_{\text{PA}}$) is -8.44 kcal/mol,²⁴ indicating that the doping of PA into the salt structure could lead to the formation of a strong ionic bond interaction. Based on this result, we envisage ionic hydrogen bonding in salt structures of PA-doped iCOF composed of sulfonate/DMAP (PA@DMAP/TpPa-SO₃H). Further, we demonstrate the convenient synthesis of iCOF by condensation reaction between Tp building block and DMAP/Pa-SO₃H as a novel C2 symmetry linker under solvothermal conditions, improving their electrochemical and thermal properties (Scheme 1b). The DMAP/Pa-SO₃H salt linker obtained from the simple acid-base transformation of Pa-SO₃H and DMAP in DMF at room temperature was characterized by ¹H, ¹³C NMR, SEM and EDX analysis (Figure 1). Moreover, β -ketoenamine provides the rigid backbone for realizing uninterrupted proton conduction.²⁵⁻²⁷

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Synthesis of DMAP/Pa-SO₃H.

2,5-Diaminobenzenesulfonic acid (0.188g, 1 mmol) was dissolved in 10 mL of DMF under stirring condition at RT. *N,N*-dimethylpyridin-4-amine (0.14g, 1.1 mmol) was added into the above solution and stirred for 4 h at 50 °C. After cooling to RT, 100 mL of THF was added to

the reaction mixture, allowed to stir for 10 minutes and filtered to get 0.28g (85% yield) of desired compound. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) 8.17 (d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2 H), 6.95 (s, 1 H), 6.89 (d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2 H), 6.44 (s, 2 H), 6.09 (s, 4 H), 3.12 (s, 6 H); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) 156.4, 140.7, 136.2, 135.7, 131.5, 117.7, 116.9, 114.6, 106.9, 39.4

Synthesis of TpPa-SO₃H.

Triformylphloroglucinol (Tp, 0.15g, 0.71 mmol), 2,5-diaminobenzenesulfonic acid (0.202g, 1.07 mmol), and 8 mL of mixture of solvent (DMAc:o-DCB, 3:1 v/v) with 0.8 mL of 6M AcOH were taken in a reaction tube. After sonication for 10 minutes, the reaction mixture was flash frozen at 77 K and degassed by three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. The reaction tube was sealed off and heated at 120 °C for 72 h. After cooling to RT, the red precipitate was filtered and washed with DMAc for several times followed by solvent exchange with acetone for 6-7 times and dried under vacuum to get the corresponding COF in ~80% yield.

Synthesis of TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H.

Triformylphloroglucinol (Tp, 0.1g, 0.48 mmol), 4-(dimethylamino)pyridin-1-ium 2,5-diaminobenzenesulfonate (0.22g, 0.72 mmol), 8 mL of mixture of solvent (DMAc:o-DCB, 3:1 v/v) were mixed taken in a reaction tube. After sonication for 10 minutes, the reaction mixture was flash frozen at 77 K and degassed by three freeze-pump-thaw cycles. The reaction tube was sealed off and heated at 120 °C for 72 h. After cooling to RT, the red precipitate was filtered and washed with DMAc for several times followed by solvent exchange with acetone for 6-7 times and dried under vacuum to get the corresponding COF in ~85% yield.

H₃PO₄ loading inside COFs.

15 mL of H₃PO₄ was added to 150 mg of COF and stirred for 120 minutes at RT. Then the suspension was filtered, washed with copious amount of water to remove adsorbed acid on the surface of COFs followed by drying under vacuum for 6 h.

Preparation of SPEEK membranes

SPEEK was synthesized from PEEK by following the literature procedure.²⁸ The SPEEK was dissolved in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide at 80 °C at constant stirring for 1 h. The obtained solution was poured into petri dish and dried to get transparent SPEEK membrane. In order to get SPEEK/DMAP membrane, DMAP was added into dissolved SPEEK in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide solution and stirred for 2 h at 80 °C, followed by drying on petri dish. PA@SPEEK/DMAP was obtained from dispersion of SPEEK/DMAP in PA at 80 °C for 6 h and then dried under vacuum.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The FTIR spectra of COFs confirmed the complete consumption of reactants and the formation of desired products (Figure 2a). The absence of a band at $\sim 1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (aldehyde band) indicates the consumption of Tp, and the condensation reaction is complete. In addition, the lack of imine (C=N) vibrations at 1620 cm^{-1} and the appearance of a band at $\sim 1576\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to a new C=C bond suggests the formation of a keto tautomer. The band at $\sim 1227\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the formation of the C-N bond. The S-OH stretching mode of $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ is observed at $\sim 1025\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1080 cm^{-1} .²⁹ Furthermore, the observed band at 2814 cm^{-1} for TpDMAP/Pa- SO_3H is assigned to vibrations of the $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ moiety confirming the presence of salt structure within the pores of iCOF.^{30,31} Moreover, doping of H_3PO_4 over COFs is confirmed by additional bands at 985 and 490 cm^{-1} corresponding to the P=O bond of H_2PO_4^- (Figure S4). The $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ band is shifted to 2835 cm^{-1} for PA@TpDMAP/Pa- SO_3H owing to the interaction of $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ with PA.

Scheme 1. a) Binding energy for model organic salt and b) synthetic route for DMAP/Pa-SO₃H, TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H.

Figure 1. a) ¹H NMR, b) ¹³C NMR, c) SEM image, d) EDX spectrum of DMAP/Pa-SO₃H.

Figure 2. a) FTIR spectra of COFs compared with the precursors. b) Experimental PXR D of TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H compared with simulated one. c) Simulated pore width and interlayer stacking of TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H.

The powder XRD analysis of the COFs showed diffraction peaks at 2θ of 4.7°, 14.31°, and 26.3-27.1°, which are assigned to (100), (110) and (001) crystal planes, respectively (Figure

2b). The crystallinity of these COFs could be attributed to keto-enol tautomerization, which hinders long range ordered stacking.³² The broad peak observed for experimental PXRD might be due to smaller particle size of COFs. The deviation of simulated PXRD observed from experimental PXRD pattern was consistent with the reported literature.^{18,26} The calculated π - π stacking distance for the (001) crystal plane was ~ 3.3 and 2.9 Å for TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H, respectively (Figure 2c and Figure S3). The simulated PXRD patterns obtained from eclipsed (AA) and staggered (AB) stacking modes both showed a degree of interlayer slip-stacking in their DFT-relaxed configurations. The simulated PXRD patterns of the eclipsed stacking model matched well with the experimental PXRD patterns of respective COFs. The deviation of experimental PXRD peaks from those of simulated is due to a smaller particle size of COFs.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of both COFs revealed three step weight loss. The first degradation step at 40-100 °C is due to the expulsion of residual solvents, the second decomposition step at 250-310 °C is owing to the rupture of sulfonic acid, and the third one at about 400 °C corresponds to the decomposition of COF backbone (Figure S5). The slightly higher stability of TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H at second disintegration stage might be attributed to the conversion of sulfonic acid into salt). Particularly, DMAP/Pa-SO₃H itself showed very low thermal stability. However, TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H made of DMAP/Pa-SO₃H linker retained higher thermal stability owing to rigid skeleton of COF and DMAP moieties toward the pore channels. The permanent porosity of COFs was determined by nitrogen adsorption isotherm using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) methods. The pore size of both COFs was found to be 2.21 nm, which matches well with the theoretically calculated value (Figure S6, and S7). The BET surface area of TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H was calculated to be 247 and 987 m² g⁻¹ respectively. The nitrogen adsorption isotherm represents the prominent hysteresis loop of type-IV isotherm, which could be related to the capillary condensation in mesopores.^{33,34}

The solid-state ^{13}C NMR (CP-MAS spectra) of TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/SO₃H revealed the formation of expected products (Figure S8). The peak at 183 ppm indicates carbonyl carbon present in both COFs. For TpDMAP/SO₃H, the peak at 40 ppm is arising from carbon of dimethylamino group which confirms the formation of desired product. The morphology of the COFs was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) measurements. The SEM images show aggregated particle morphology (Figure S9). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of COFs indicate that they possess layered structural morphology with porous structure (Figure S10).

The XPS analysis was carried out for both COFs to probe their interaction and chemical composition (Figure S11). The binding energy of N1s in TpPa-SO₃H indicates two types of nitrogen, one at 400.4 eV for secondary amine (-NH) and another at 402.6 eV for protonated nitrogen (-NH₂⁺).¹⁸ Alternatively, N1s peak for TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H shows three different nitrogens, one at 401.4 eV for secondary amine (-NH), the second peak at 403.5 eV corresponds to protonated pyridine nitrogen (pyridinium ion), and the third one at 405.7 eV indicates tertiary amine present on pyridine.

Figure 3. Nyquist plot for a) PA@TpPa-SO₃H, b) PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H under anhydrous condition, c) Arrhenius plot for PA@TpPa-SO₃H and PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H under anhydrous condition, d) Proton conductivity of PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H under humidified condition (80 °C and 95% RH) and anhydrous condition (140 °C) at different time intervals.

The proton conductivity of COFs was evaluated by alternative current (AC) electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements (Figure 3 and S12-15). TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H exhibited proton conductivity of 9.3×10^{-5} and 3.7×10^{-7} S cm⁻¹ respectively, at 120 °C under anhydrous conditions (Table S4). The higher conductivity of TpPa-SO₃H could be attributed to readily ionizable protons from -SO₃H groups. The limited access of ionizable protons in TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H restricts the proton conductivity to lower magnitude. Further, the proton conductivity of H₃PO₄-doped COFs was evaluated under both anhydrous and humidified conditions. H₃PO₄ doped TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H were denoted as

PA@TpPa-SO₃H and PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H respectively. PA@TpPa-SO₃H showed maximum proton conductivity of 3.7×10^{-4} S cm⁻¹ while PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H displayed 1.6×10^{-2} S cm⁻¹ at 140 °C under anhydrous conditions (Table S4). The high proton conductivity of PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H is attributed to organic salt that could enhance ionic hydrogen bonding interaction with PA which holds them within the pore. As a result, extended hydrogen bonding and high amount of proton source (phosphoric acid) which actively participates in proton hopping within the pore channels ensures uninterrupted flow of proton migration.^{35,36} Further, this dense hydrogen bonding provides a greater number of protons hopping sites at molecular level with lower energy of activation. From the Arrhenius plots, the calculated activation energy (E_a) was 0.29 eV and 0.19 eV for PA@TpPa-SO₃H and PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H, respectively, which follows the Grotthuss mechanism (Figure 3c). The lower activation energy of PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H provides facile protons hopping via ionic hydrogen bonding along the pore channels. Further, E_a remains nearly unchanged for both COFs. However, there is a significant difference observed in the frequency factor (i.e., the intercept of the line). Since the frequency factor represents the likelihood of collisions between reactants, the higher intercept for PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H suggests that DMAP facilitates the formation of dense hydrogen bonding via interaction with doped PA, which would enhance proton hopping. Moreover, PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H provides notably comparable anhydrous proton conductivity among the reported COFs (Table S6).^{37,38} In addition, both as-synthesized COFs exhibited higher proton conductivity at 80 °C under humidified conditions (95% RH) over the corresponding COFs measured under anhydrous conditions (Figure S14-15 and Table S4 & S5). As the humidity increases, the conductivity also increases due to the higher number of adsorbed water molecules, resulting in the migration of protons. The maximum proton conductivity of 4.2×10^{-3} and 5.2×10^{-4} S cm⁻¹ was observed for TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H respectively at 80 °C, 95% RH. Moreover, PA@TpPa-SO₃H and PA@TpDMAP/Pa-

SO₃H showed the highest proton conductivity of 1.3×10^{-2} and 1.8×10^{-2} S cm⁻¹ respectively, at 80 °C, and 95% RH. The higher proton conductivity of PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H could be due to the enhanced ionic hydrogen bonding interaction between organic salt and PA within the pore channels. Furthermore, proton conductivity of PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H at low humidity (40% RH) is notably higher than that of other samples (Figure S16). This indicates that the presence of dense protonic acid groups can achieve high proton conductivity even in lower amount of adsorbed water. At higher humidity, the presence of adsorbed water further enhances proton conductivity. The long-term stability of proton conductivity was probed by recording AC electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements at the interval of 2 h. The continuous exposure of PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H to anhydrous condition (at 140 °C) leads to decline in proton conductivity after 2 h, while maximum proton conductivity was retained after 72 h exposure to humidified condition at 80 °C, 95% RH (Figure 4d and S17-18).

Moreover, to examine the adaptability of a dual-acid system in other acid-modified polymeric membranes, we selected 83% sulfonated poly(ether ether ketone), SPEEK. We prepared three membranes as SPEEK, SPEEK/DMAP, and PA@SPEEK/DMAP and evaluated their proton conductivity under anhydrous and humidified conditions (Figure 4 & S20-23 and Table S7&8). The maximum proton conductivity observed for PA@SPEEK/DMAP was 1.2×10^{-2} S cm⁻¹, which is about 100-fold higher than that of SPEEK membrane at 120 °C under anhydrous condition. Similarly, the high proton conductivity of 2.4×10^{-2} S cm⁻¹ was observed for PA@SPEEK/DMAP at 80 °C and 95% RH, which is 10-fold higher compared to SPEEK under similar conditions. However, proton conductivity is drastically reduced at 140 °C, which could be attributed to the degradation of the DMAP moiety present in 1D chain of the SPEEK polymer at higher temperatures (Figure S21). As a result, a common polymer SPEEK with dual acid moieties showed high conductivity at medium temperature (120 °C) under anhydrous condition and retained the order of 10^{-2} S cm⁻¹ at 80 °C and 40 ~ 95% RH. The loss of proton

conductivity to large extent was registered for PA@SPEEK/DMAP after continuous exposure to anhydrous condition for 2 h (Figure S24-26). However, prolonged exposure to humidified condition (80 °C, 95% RH) retained its initial proton conductivity over 48 h. Thus, this dual acid system is expected to have potential industry applications.

Figure 4. a) Arrhenius plot for SPEEK membranes under anhydrous conditions. b) Comparison of proton conductivity under humidified conditions. c) Film images of SPEEK, SPEEK/DMAP and PA@SPEEK/DMAP.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we demonstrated organic salt incorporated ionic covalent organic frameworks as proton conducting material, and verified the practical opportunities of the system. The impregnation of phosphoric acid as an external proton source into the iCOF cavity constructed dual acid-tailored moieties, and significantly improved the proton conductivity. Further, the incorporated proton source would not only improve thermal stability of iCOF via dual-acid moieties (dual ionic bonds via DMAP), but also suppress acid leaching. Moreover, the high

concentration of multiple proton carriers in the pores of acid-tailored iCOF (PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H), generate an infinite H-bond network and low energy barrier for proton, enabling efficient proton hopping throughout 1D channels. Thus, the proton conductivity of PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H is about two orders elevated over to that of sulfonic acid-based parent covalent organic frameworks (PA@TpPa-SO₃H) under similar experimental conditions. Notably, the highest proton conductivity of $1.56 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ was observed for PA@TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H at 140 °C under anhydrous conditions. This is the first report for dual acid system on the pore wall of COFs. By using this strategy on a common polymeric SPEEK membrane, proton conductivity was achieved similar to the ionic COF. Thus, this research could open up the possibility of dual acid systems in other acid modified polymer materials such as SPEEK, sulfated silk fibroin (SSF), Nafion, and etc.

ASSOCIATED CONTENTS

Supporting information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

Detailed synthesis of organic salt linker (DMAP/Pa-SO₃H) monomer, TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H, TGA, FT-IR, BET analysis, SEM, TEM, Nyquist plots of TpPa-SO₃H and TpDMAP/Pa-SO₃H under anhydrous and moist conditions (PDF)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

Atsushi Nagai: Next-Generation Energy Systems group, Centre of Excellence ENSEMBLE3 sp. z o.o., Wólczyńska 133, Warsaw 01-919, Poland.

Email: atsushi.nagai@ensemble3.eu

Authors

Vellaichamy Joseph: Next-Generation Energy Systems group, Centre of Excellence ENSEMBLE3 sp. z o.o., Wólczyńska 133, Warsaw 01-919, Poland.

Keiichiro Maegawa: Next-Generation Energy Systems group, Centre of Excellence ENSEMBLE3 sp. z o.o., Wólczyńska 133, Warsaw 01-919, Poland.

Mateusz Wlazło: Chemical and Biological Systems Simulation Lab, Centre of New Technologies, University of Warsaw, Banacha 2c, 02-097 Warsaw, Poland.

Marek J. Potrzebowski: Center of Molecular and Macromolecular Studies, Polish Academy of Sciences, Sienkiewicza 112, Lodz 90-363, Poland.

Krzysztof Łyczko: Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology, Dorodna 16, Warsaw 03-195, Poland.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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